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PERFORMANCE OF NRHM IN PROMOTING RURAL HEALTH IN INDIA

Dr. Kabita Kumari Sahu

Lecturer in Economics,
North Orissa University, Baripada, Odisha , India

Abstract

The objective of the paper is to analyze the trend and components wise of fund allocation and pattern of utilization under NRHM to promote rural health care system in India with special reference to Odisha. The paper is based on secondary data collected from Health Statistics & NRHM data. The analysis is based on growth rates, correlation, regression, percentage change, line graphs and t test. The rural population in India was recorded at 70 percent of the total 1.24 billion in 2011. Only 30 per cent of the government's public health spending went to the rural health system that served 70 per cent of the Indian population. Majority of rural residents in India do not have any type of health insurance and are experiencing very limited access to health care. The National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) was launched on 12th April 2005 which seeks to provide accessible, affordable and quality health care to rural populations, especially vulnerable and underserved population groups in the Country. The Mission achieved infant mortality rate (IMR) of 30 per 1000 live births, maternal mortality 100 per 100 thousand live births and total fertility rate of 2.1 by the year 2012. After the implementation of NRHM programme, health care status has very impressive record. Health care indicator IMR declined from 62 to 42 and MMR declined from 301 to 178 in 2011. Fund allocation under NRHM of GOI provides impressive amount in 2005-06 with Rs 4433.99 crore allocated. It has increased to Rs.17030.68 crore in 2012-13. There is significant increasing trend in fund allocation under NRHM but pattern of utilization is not satisfactory.

Key Words: Fund Allocation, Health Care, Pattern, Trend, Utilisation

Introduction

National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) was launched in 2005 to provide effective health care to the rural population throughout the country with special focus on 18 states having weak public health indicators and/or weak health infrastructure. It was launched with the objective of improving the access to quality healthcare especially for the rural women and children and in strengthening of health infrastructure, capacity building, and decentralised planning. The Mission aims at effective integration of health with determinants of health like sanitation and hygiene, nutrition and safe drinking water. The mission was conceived as an umbrella programme subsuming

Odisha, one of the poorest states of the country, is vulnerable to repeated natural calamities like droughts, floods and cyclones. The recurring natural calamities further exacerbate distress of the

people, particularly small and marginal farmers and landless laborers. The agrarian structure predominated by small and marginal farmers whose capacity to invest is limited. The poor agricultural productivity resulted in virtually stagnant agricultural growth and employment generation. That, further, has an adverse effect on the health status of the people. Deficient in infrastructure- railways, paved roads, ports and telecommunication-limits the optimal exploitation of its vast natural resources and the followed industrial growth. On the other hand poor infrastructural development in hilly terrains of western and southern Odisha, many rural communities are physically excluded from the rest of the state and denied access to essential socio-economic amenities like schools and hospitals. As a result of which birth rate, death rate, infant mortality rate, life expectancy rate, maternal mortality ratio, total fertility ratio etc. lags behind the national average .To improve the prevailing situation, the Government of Odisha launched the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) programme through the state on 17th June 2005. NRHM has completed its six years of journey in Odisha. It becomes necessary to assess the impact of NRHM on the health indicators, to know how the schemes under NRHM are working in Odisha and to assess the transition in the health status of Odisha. NRHM has been functioning under the overall guidance of the "State Health Mission" headed by the Chief Minister of the State. The function under the Mission has been carried out through the Odisha State Health & Family Welfare Society. The SPMU/Mission Directorate is acting as the Secretariat to the State Health Mission as well as the State Health Society, Headed by an Executive Director/Mission Director.

Recognising health as an essential component of development and in assuring basic level of health care to the population, the 11th Five Year plan contemplated to facilitate convergence and development of public health systems and services that are responsive to health needs and aspirations of people and in ensuring access to affordable health care. The 11th Five Year Plan emphasised to provide special attention to the health of marginalized groups like adolescent girls, women of all ages, children below the age of three, older persons, disabled, and tribal groups. The Plan had set time bound measurable goals to achieve, some of which are Reducing MMR to 1 per 1000 live births (100 per 100,000 live births), Reducing IMR to 28 per 1000 live births, Reducing TFR to 2.1, Reducing anaemia among women and girls by 50%, Raising the sex ratio for age group 0 to 6 to 935 by 2011-12 and 950 by 2016-17. The 11th Five Year Plan essentially focused on a number of thrust areas, including improvements in public healthcare facilities in rural areas through National Rural Health Mission, enhancing tertiary health facilities in States through Pradhan Mantri Swasthya Surakha Yojana (PMSSY), increasing health human resources by relaxing norms for setting up Medical Colleges in States and initiating measures to prevent & control the emerging problem of non-communicable diseases. The achievements of the programmes are discussed in the following paragraphs.

The National Rural Health Mission has been in operation since June 2005 in Odisha, which has been extended up to 2017. It aims to improve access of rural people especially poor women & children to equitable, affordable, accountable and effective primary health care. It aims at effective integration of health concerns with determinants of health like sanitation & hygiene, nutrition & safe drinking water through a district plan for health. It seeks decentralization of programmes for district management of health. It aims to undertake architectural correction of health system to enable it to effectively handle increased allocation as promised under the National Common minimum Programme and promote policies that strengthen public health management and services in the country. NRHM subsumes of all existing programmes like Reproductive Child Health, Immunization, National Disease Control Programme, and Integrated Disease Surveillance Project. It aims at integration of all vertical Family Health Programmes and funds for optimal utilization for infrastructure and strengthening delivery of primary health care. The mission was conceived as an umbrella programme subsuming all the then existing programmes of health and family welfare including RCH-II, National Disease Control Programmes for Malaria, TB, Kala-azar, Filariasis, Blindness and iodine deficiency. The mission targets to provide universal access to rural people to effective, equitable, affordable, and accountable primary health care. Some of the strategies employed by the mission to achieve its goals were -: promoting access to improved healthcare at household level through ASHAs, strengthening sub-centres, PHCs and CHCs, preparing and implementing of inter-sectoral district health plans and integrating vertical health programmes at all levels, envisaging health plan for each village through the Village Health

Committee, etc. In this context, the paper attempts to analyze the fund allocation and utilization under NRHM in India.

Status of Health Indicators in India

One of the important objectives of India's plan has been to raise the standard of living and subsequently health status of its population. For achieving these objectives many other factors such as education nutrition, adequate food etc. are essential but the provision of health care services to all, play the crucial role. The status of selected health indicators are shown in the table -1. India has made substantial progress in the health indicators over the past few years with regards to life expectancy at birth moved up to from 61.3years to 67.3 years during 2000-01 to 2010-11 for male and from 63 years to 69.9 years for females during same period. During 2005-06 the all India average of expectation of life at birth in rural area saw an increase compared to urban. This increase in life expectancy is a result of an overall decline significantly from 66(2001) to 42 in 2011, and also decline the maternal mortality rate from 301(2001) to 178in the year 2011. And total fertility rate also declined from 3.1 to 2.4 in the same period.

Table: 1 Status of Health Indicators in India

Health Indicators	2001	2005	2011
Crude Birth Rate	25.4	23.08	21.6
Crude Death Rate	8.4	7.6	7
Infant Mortality Rate	66	58	42
Maternal Mortality Rate	301	254	178
Total Fertility Rate	3.1	2.9	2.4

Source : Population Census 2001 and 2011

Health Expenditure in India

Public Health expenditure is an important component of analyzing health scenario in India. Table-2 illustrates the growth of public expenditure on Health sector in India. In the year 2000-01, the total public expenditure on health in India stood at Rs. 2472.33 crore.

Table-2 Public expenditure on Health in India (Rs in Crores)

Year	Expenditure	Growth Rates(%)
2000-01	2472.33	--
2001-02	2826.61	14.33
2002-03	3028.04	7.13
2003-04	3761.12	24.21
2004-05	4311.37	14.63
2005-06	6684.49	55.04
2006-07	8325.66	24.55
2007-08	10726.78	28.84
2008-09	13750.50	28.19
2009-10	15888.84	15.55
2010-11	18641.47	17.32
2011-12	19447.67	4.32
2012 -13	24261.06	24.75

Source: Compiled from Various Annual financial statements of GOI

It drastically increased to that of Rs. 18641.47 crore in the year 2010-11. It registered a CAGR of 20.16 per cent over the period from 2000-01 to 2010-11. On an average, the public health

expenditure in India during this period has increased with an annual growth rate of 23 percent. It is expected to reach Rs. 19447.67 crore in the year 2011-12 (as per the revised estimates of the Union Budget). For the year 2012-13, the Budget estimates for health sector in India is earmarked at Rs. 24261.06 crore, with an increase of 12.14 per cent over the previous year 2011-12 budget. During the period 2005-06, there was comparatively higher increase in the public health expenditure as seen by the annual growth rate of that period. It had increased to the tune of 55.04 per cent over the period 2004-05.

Fund Allocation and Utilization under NRHM in India

Fund Flow in NRHM integrates all related; inter linked and stand-alone schemes in the health sector including RCH, National Disease Control Programs (NDCP), Integrated Disease Surveillance as well as new initiatives proposed under NRHM and National Commission on Macro Economics and Health. A common and flexible fiscal pool has been designed to cover all NRHM activities and various financial resources including external aid have been rationalized and compressed into four categories. These include: (i) operational support to states (released through treasury route); (ii) operational cost of institution supported by MOHFW; (iii) activities centrally implemented; and (iv) activities in the State Programme Implementation Plan (released through State Health Societies). Support for the District Health Action Plans falls under the category of support to activities in the State PIP.

The NRHM Funds are Released to States through Integrated Health Societies under following Components:

- 1) Reproductive and Child Health Programme (RCH Flexipool)
- 2) Additionalities under NRHM (Mission Flexipool)
- 3) Routine Immunization (including Pulse Polio) (RI)
- 4) National Disease Control Programs (NDCP)

NRHM also aims to increase public health expenditure by 10% annually during the mission period and the states are expected to contribute 15% of the outlay annually towards health. Following the submission of state PIP, the National Program Co- ordination Committee (NPCC) approves the same and funds are released for the upcoming financial year. The funds are transferred to the State Health Society in four components and additionally, the society will receive the state's share of 15% of the total outlay. The funds are generally released to states in 3 or 4 trenches upon submission of Utilization Certificate and other documents. GOI in the year 2005-06 implemented one of the health related flag ship programme namely National Rural Health mission. Before the implementation of this programme, government spent on very less amount for the health centre. it's nearly 0.90 percent of the GNP but its expenditure increases silently after implementation of this programme. GoI gives more importance to health sector through NRHM programme and that's way government release for more fund to NRHM programme. In 2005-06 Rs. 4633.39 crore was allocated for the programme and Rs. 4433.75 crore released by government but expenditure amount is only Rs. 3204.17 crore. Upto 2007-08 expenditure was less than the release fund, but after 2008-09 allocation and release fund increased with decreasing rate but expenditure incurred was seen more than allocation and release fund up to 2011-12. In the year 2012-13 allocation is Rs. 17030.68 crore and released fund is Rs.14935.21 crore but expenditure is Rs. 16944.26 crore. After the implementation of this programme, Government of India has given more importance to increasing Health care infrastructure facilities, RCH flexi pool and NRHM flexi pool and that's way expenditure was seen more than allocation and release fund. Table-3 depicts the overall fund disbursement since the implementation of NRHM Programme. It also shows the Percentage of expenditure incurred on components under NRHM. 28.05 percent of amount spent is for RCH flexipool, 30.50 percent is spent on NRHM flexipool, and highest percentage is for Infrastructure maintenance which is about 30.92 percent of the total expenditure under NRHM programme. But expenditure incurred on IPPI (pulse polio) component are

very low, its value is only 3.7 percent and further 6.77 percent is on NDCP components under NRHM in India From 2005-06 to 2012-13.

Table-3 Percentage on components under NRHM from 2005-06 to 2012-13

Year	Allocation	Release	Expenditure	
Components under NRHM	Allocation	Released	Expenditure	% of expenditure
RCH Flexipool (Including Routine Immunization)	25321.2	22714.7	24424.7	28.05
NRHM Flexipool	26188	25286	26605.9	30.56
Infrastructure Maintenance	23325.4	24397.6	26926.4	30.92
IPPI (Pulse Polio)	3603.22	3324.05	3264.26	3.76
National Disease Control Programme (NDCP)	8207.16	6501.29	5838.64	6.71

Source: NRHM.nic.in MIS Report 2013.

Figure-1 Percentage of Expenditure on components to the total expenditure under NRHM

Source: NRHM.nic.in MIS Report 2013.

Overview of the total fund allocation from 2005-06 to 2012-13 indicates that allocation is Rs. 86344.82crore. Out of this total allocation 95 per cent is being released which is about Rs. 82029.96 Crore and expenditure incurred since the implementation of the programme on components under NRHM on is 87079.59 crores which is (101.50) percent of the allocation. That's way expenditure is more than allocation and released in same period. Data has shown in the below table-4.

Table-4 Total allocation, Release and expenditure from 2005-06 to 2012-13

Allocation	Released	Expenditure
86644.92	82223.61	87059.81
100 %	95%	101%

Source: NRHM.nic.in MIS Report 2013.

After the implementation of NRHM programme, health care status has very impressive record. Health care indicator IMR declined from 62 to 42 and MMR declined from 301 to 178 in 2011. Fund allocation under NRHM provides impressive amount in 2005-06 with Rs 4433.99 crore allocated. It has increased to Rs.17030.68 crore in 2012-13. And released fund has also increased from Rs 4433.75 cores to Rs 14935.21 crore in the same period. But expenditure is very satisfied. It has increased to Rs 3204.17 crore to Rs 16944.26 crore in the same period. Further the share is more

than the amount allocated and released in the recent years. One more important point is to find out component-wise expenditure. GOI has spent more than 88 per cent on RCH flexi pool, NRHM flexi pool and Infrastructure maintenance and very less amount is spent on IPPI and NDCP.

Constraints of NRHM

National Rural Health Mission has various constraints, which are discussed below;

- 1) **Awareness:** Through systematic campaigns on a continuing basis PRIs, staff and NGOs at village level should create awareness among rural people of all age groups about various types of health facilities available. Print and electronic media have a significant role and responsibility to create awareness and facilitate bridging the gaps between the demand and supply of health services. Some villages have no health centre and the government hospital is quite afar. Interaction with some people revealed that they have not availed delivery facilities in the hospital because of lack of awareness. It is the personal factor which is affecting policy intervention for which massive awareness campaign is needed.
- 2) **Training:** Since many ASHAs in tribal, hilly and backward regions may not have educational qualifications required to perform responsibilities under NRHM they need to be trained frequently for capacity building and performance monitored.
- 3) **Review:** At the district and State level quarterly review of implementation must focus on correcting district and State-wise imbalances, achieving integration and convergence of different programs, adequate funding to bridge gaps in infrastructure and inculcating patient-friendly attitude in staff.
- 4) **Monitoring:** Right to health is recognized as an inalienable right of all citizens as incorporated in the relevant rulings by the Supreme Court as well as the International Conventions to which India is a signatory. As rights convey guaranteed entitlement to the citizens, the monitoring authority has to ensure their compliance. Since decentralized planning, preparation of district health plans, community ownership of the health delivery system and inter-sectoral convergence. Monitoring periodic public hearings and grievance redressal system should make health service providers accountable to the community and beneficiaries. Organizing periodic independent household and facility surveys can identify gaps in the planning and implementation of NRHM to provide quality health services.
- 5) **Community Empowerment:** Experience suggests that rural communities suffer denial to access healthcare in many respects, viz. [i] treatment not given or patient not attended on time; insulting or discriminatory behaviour of staff; inadequate attention given to the patient [ii] non-availability of staff (doctor or nurse), medicines, essential equipment/infrastructure, transport facility for referring the patient outside for investigations [iii] charges more than specified; denial on grounds of inability to pay user fees. Consequences of denial are serious, some times resulting in death of the patient, adverse health consequences, temporary or permanent physical damage or disability; financial loss to patient and the family. Community empowerment is, therefore, a sine qua non to guarantee individual's right to health care by putting community pressure on health providers. PRIs, Community based organizations, NGOs, Civil Societies, Self-Help-Groups etc. should be empowered to demand quality public health services and make service providers accountable.
- 6) **Shortage of Funds:** Shortage of funds is a major drawback in public sector for rural health, this leads to non-availability of health infrastructure, provision of inputs, drugs etc at grass root level. In rural areas improving nutrition seems to be the biggest challenge.

Policy Recommendations

Though there has been a significant improvement in the health status of the people, some possible strategies for adoption by the state to improve the health status further have been suggested below.

- 1) Both the government organizations and non-government organization should put their combined effort to bring reforms in the health system in the rural areas of Odisha.
- 2) □ Free education up to higher secondary level should be given to SC and ST people. After the return of the mother and the child after delivery from the hospital, the domiciliary and clinical based follow up should be carried out by both ASHA and MPHW (F).
- 3) Public Private Partnership should be given due importance in order to fill up the large gap in the field.
- 4) NGOs along with ASHAs and AWWs should spread the health awareness among the illiterate people of the region.
- 5) Public involvement in solving health problems as well as suggesting improvement is ensured through Rogi Kalayan Samities.
- 6) The Public, Private and NGO/Third Sectors Partnership should put combined effort to bring reforms in the health system in the rural areas of India.
- 7) The facility is not reaching all the groups. Government should extend effectively the facility to the hilly region people and tribal people.
- 8) After the implementation of NRHM health indicators like crude death rate, infant and maternal mortality can be reduced significantly. So Government has to promote this programme extensively.

Conclusion

NRHM was launched in India to provide effective health care with specific focus on the backward districts. The poor and marginalized which includes women were to be given special attention under the programme. It has adopted a comprehensive approach by including the departments of Panchayat Raj, Women and Child Development, Rural Water Supply and Sanitation and Education. This is different from the previous approaches to ameliorate health problems of the rural poor. NRHM launched by Government of India holds great hopes and promises to serve the deprived communities of rural areas. The invariable existence of socio cultural difference in the community has always been a major challenge to the healthcare efforts made by the Government, particularly in the rural areas where illiteracy is more. If Government continuously and effectively implement this programme, then there is no doubt that India can reduce its Infant Mortality and Maternal Mortality as per the requirements of Millennium Development.

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